

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE SOURCES OF PSYCHOLOGICAL STRESS AND THE LEVEL OF SELF-ESTEEM AMONG FOOTBALL REFEREES

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Abstract:

This survey aims at revealing the relationship of sources of psychological stress to the level of self-esteem. It focused mainly on the following questions:

- Is there a correlation between fear of physical abuse and self-esteem?
- Is there a correlation between rewards, incentives, and self-esteem?
- Is there a correlation between conflict of social dimension and level of self-esteem?
- Is there a correlation between media dimension and level of self-esteem?
- Is there a correlation between physical condition, time and level of self-esteem?
- Is there a correlation between fear of failure and level of self-esteem?
- Is there a correlation between personal conflict and level of self-esteem?
- Is there a correlation between media dimension and level of self-esteem?

The survey suggested a number of hypotheses based on the existence of a correlation between each of the dimensions of psychological stress mentioned above and the level of self-esteem. The study was based on the descriptive correlative approach as it dealt with the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variables. The sample of the study consisted of elite referees of the

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professional football division, which was chosen in a deliberate manner, and reached 80 referees. The following tools have been used: the self-assessment scale prepared by Hussein Abdel Aziz Al-Derini and Mohamad Ahmad Oussama, Abdelwahab Mohamad Kamil which has been applied and adapted by Professor Bachir Mamria on the Algerian environment, psychological sources of stress measure and initial information form. These tools were applied after estimating the psychometric properties that confirmed their suitability for use with the basic study sample. The following statistical methods have been relied on, Pearson correlation coefficient using the statistical software version 20 SPSS for statistical significance.

The study comes out with the following results:

- There is a correlation between fear of physical abuse and self-esteem.
- There is a correlation between rewards, incentives, and self-esteem.
- There is a correlation between conflict of social dimension and level of self-esteem.
- There is a correlation between media dimension and level of self-esteem.
- There is a correlation between physical condition, time and level of self-esteem.
- There is a correlation between fear of failure and level of self-esteem.
- There is a correlation between personal conflict and level of self-esteem.
- There is a correlation between media dimension and level of self-esteem.

The study outcomes have been discussed in light of the theoretical framework and the results of previous studies and concluded with a set of proposals.

Keywords: psychological stress; self-esteem; football referees

1. Introduction

Stress is one aspect of athletic performance that athletes (athletes, coaches, and referees) often experience as a natural consequence of focusing on success or fear of failure poor evaluation, inability to control, control emotions, or loss of self-confidence resulting from committing the same error or performance instability. Different studies indicate that one of the main reasons leading to the failure of most athletes or inability to reach the maximum possible performance is the ability to focus attention during the psychological stress. (Shamoon, Al-Jamal, 1996 and Mustafa, 2001, and Al-Saka 2003, Crocker & Isaak, 1997)

The researchers believe that the more an individual knows the limits of his abilities, the more effective it is to interact with different life situations without problems or psychological conflicts. This goes in line with what Pandora referred to in

1982, where he believes that the concept of the individual about himself is a key factor in the definition and interpretation of human behavior. The effectiveness of the self-perception affects the patterns of thinking and behavior and emotional excitement, the higher the level of self-efficacy, the higher the achievement and the abandonment of failure experiences as well as self-regulation of reflexes. (Bandura, 1982.P122)

Even the sport, which was practiced for fun and entertainment, has become a great human development in one of the important economic areas, especially football, which is the number one game in the sequence of games.

Specialists have always sought to develop the game and make it the most attractive among sports because it attracts the attention of most of the masses of sports because of the fun of performance and pleasure in follow-up. Even when setting the game regulations, the main goals targeted are the public enjoyment as well as the safety of players and equality between the two teams, and it was stressed to the referees of football to avoid mistakes and maintain the safety of players and pleasure through watching a beautiful game where law is wisely and perfectly applied.

Based on the above, we recognize that the law is a tool to make more glamour for football and therefore specialists and researchers focused on referees in the implementation of the law of the game in the stadiums in terms of physical and psychological rehabilitation and other qualifications that make them able to successfully and accurately manage matches in football. With this big interest of specialists, spectators, players and the media in all its forms, which in turn put great pressure on the rulers of football causing many parties, football referees have become in need of those who support them, especially that scientific studies about the referees in our country are almost non-existent.

Football refereeing is one of the main factors underlying the success and failure of sports competition in general and football in particular. It is noticeable in this competition that talk and controversy have been frequent at the level of arbitration and its impact on the course of the game and thus, blaming the performance of this person without returning of the competent authorities to know the real reasons behind the low level of referees through knowing and understanding at least the factors leading to it.

While good refereeing pushes players to master and concentrate on playing without protest, bad refereeing has many disadvantages that lead to the lack of benefit from the exercise of sports activity. Bad refereeing may generate riots of supporters and possible injuries adding to this rough play may be accompanied by poor refereeing, followed by lack of sportsmanship, matches, hereby, lose their educational and artistic value and therefore the whole sports activity loses a lot of spirit and pleasure, protests will also increase and cause the disappearance of the spirit of satisfaction, as well as the

social benefit, which is one of the most important foundations on which sports activity is based.

Although the sports umpire carries heavy burdens and troubles, he is happy to practice them and does not care about their problems because he is motivated by happiness and passion for the game. Therefore, he always strives to succeed through continuous work, including physical and technical obligations, and this is the culmination of development and success to reach the highest levels.

The referee's self-esteem is considered an important dimension in sports activity. One of the qualities of the character of sports referee, which has become a criterion of effectiveness, appreciation for itself, which has the greatest impact on the personality of players, coaches and administrators. (Mohamed Jamal Abdel Moneim, 2008, p14)

2. The main problem

The negative result of psychological pressure is one of the most important topics that still receive attention and controversy research widely among researchers because of its harmful effects on the individual and society in general.

Persistent psychological stress and, in the case of negative adjustment, can lead to a severe and sustained emotional response, and physical, psychological, and behavioral complications that make football rule deviate from normal performance, knowing that the impact of these pressures depends on the nature of the personality, and the ability to withstand frustration, flexibility, or level of optimism.

Although pressure is considered necessary and a catalyst factor for stabilizing the internal balance and biological rhythm of the individual, the increase in stress or the duration of exposure beyond the capacity of adaptation may lead to the emergence and development of diseases.

Sports arbitration is an activity that is always associated with stress. The referee is often subject to questioning his integrity or his honesty to the accountability by athletes in general (trainers, players, administrators, audience, and media). In sports, it's the referee who is often seen negatively as the losers always blame their mistakes on him, and he is rarely mentioned by the winning team, let alone the criticism and sometimes unjustified attack on him in the media by coaches, players and administrators. (Constbal, 1996)

The performance of sports judgment is linked to many factors of psychological stress, which vary in intensity and types, which may lead to physical and mental exhaustion in a manner that affects the level of physical and psychological abilities in

general, and the ability to control the emotions or the ability to make the right decision in particular. (Harun 1998, Mustafa 2001, Constbal, 1996)

Teppel (2001) points out that the unique roles and tasks of governance may be a major source of pressure on the referee. He believes that there are three roles to be played by the referee: to act as a negotiator to discuss and resolve the tension between the two contenders, as a judge who applies the rules and regulations of the game and to make appropriate decisions, and finally acts as a guide and supervisor to all participants to manage everything that happens in competition. In contrast, the perception of competitors of these roles is different, which may lead to continuing conflict between participants in most competitions and in a way that requires the government to resolve these differences.

Weinberg and Richardson (1990) stress that such unique roles and tasks are often a major cause of stress, and anxiety, especially as referees are often subject to criticism and public discussion by the masses. On the other hand, the referee's success is not noticed or evaluated only by a few.

The referee's success in managing the competition depends on his ability to make quick decision during a fraction of a second; this affects handling the pressure on him whenever he tried to reach competition to safety, especially that studies indicate that the psychological pressure on the referees of sports in general and football in particular, are a major obstacle to the instability and development of their performance during the management of the competition.

As the study of self-esteem is one of the important topics that still top the basic concepts in research related to the psychology of sports personality, with the submitted effort and since referees are subjected to a huge pressure from different sides, there are various positions in sports competitions about which the referee may choose a decision he thinks right and correct, while the defeated team and its fans regard it as one of the biggest mistakes and foul on them, and may be overlooked by the winning team and fans.

These situations show the anger of the masses through verbal abuse and cheers that increase the pressure on the government, which in turn increases the rates of mental and physical disorders to prevent the right judgment and that has a significant impact on the referee's personality, leading to a defect in the important aspects of character, namely, the self-esteem (Muhammad Jamal Abdel-Moneim, 2008, p. 15). Thus, the ability to self-awareness or self-esteem is the first step toward understanding sports referee for himself, his ability to change and prepare himself in a good way despite the importance of self-esteem in the field of sports activities in general and the field of arbitration in particular.

This problem has led us to ask the following general question:

Is there a relationship between the sources of psychological stress and the level of self-esteem in football referees?

By answering the following questions:

- Is there a correlation between fear of physical abuse and self-esteem?
- Is there a correlation between rewards, incentives, and self-esteem?
- Is there a correlation between conflict of social dimension and level of self-esteem?
- Is there a correlation between media dimension and level of self-esteem?
- Is there a correlation between physical condition, time and level of self-esteem?
- Is there a correlation between fear of failure and level of self-esteem?
- Is there a correlation between personal conflict and level of self-esteem?
- Is there a correlation between media dimension and level of self-esteem?

3. The research hypotheses

3.1 General hypothesis

There is a relationship between the sources of psychological stress and the level of self-esteem in football referees.

3.2 Partial hypotheses:

- There is a correlation between fear of physical abuse and self-esteem.
- There is a correlation between rewards, incentives, and self-esteem.
- There is a correlation between conflict of social dimension and level of self-esteem.
- There is a correlation between media dimension and level of self-esteem.
- There is a correlation between physical condition, time and level of self-esteem.
- There is a correlation between fear of failure and level of self-esteem.
- There is a correlation between personal conflict and level of self-esteem.
- There is a correlation between media dimension and level of self-esteem.

3.3 The importance of the study

The stress subject among football referees derives its importance from the fact that it has not received attention in Arab studies in general and in the Algerian environment in particular, and regarding the serious negative repercussions that may result from persistent psychological stress on the level of self-esteem and performance of referees, this study came to address the issue of these pressures in order to know the levels of the

referees, which helps in judging whether the level of pressure is moderate or it reached levels that may pose a danger to the health of the referees, which requires the attention of researchers and guardians in view to work on the development of strategies that manage the pressures to make them at healthy levels and do not even affect their level of self-esteem.

This study provides a list of the most important sources and causes of psychological stress, which are reflected in the level of self-esteem from the point of view of members of the study community, which makes it easier for officials and guardians to develop a mechanism to address these pressures according to their importance or rather degree of seriousness and thus achieve satisfaction in work, which may result from psychological stress.

3.4 Objectives of the study

1. To identify the most important causes and sources of psychological stress on the personality of football referees.
2. To know the level of self-esteem of football referees.
3. To design the list of sources of psychological stress in the referees of football.
4. To know the levels of psychological stress in football referees.
5. To spot the light on the importance of the relationship between the various causes of stress and the level of self-esteem and some variables that affect the decisions of the referees.
6. To address the variables which affect the decisions of the referees during the management of different games.
7. The importance of guidance and psychological orientation of the referees so that they can manage games with the least mistakes.

4. Terms used in research

4.1 Psychological stress

Mills (1982) defines stress as an internal reaction resulting from an individual's inability to meet environmental requirements he is in (Awad Sultan Al-Mishaan, 2001, p. 71). It is also known as the sense of loss of balance between demands and potentials and usually accompanied by states of failure, where this failure faces demands and potential powerful influence in the psychological pressures.

4.2 Procedural definition of psychological stress

It is a state of instability resulting from mental, physical and psychological stress, which causes an individual's inability to adapt to the surrounding environment and the many requirements that fall upon him, and his inability to meet these requirements. Because of the lack of help of people surrounding to overcome these pressures, the individual reaches a state of frustration and depression and may reach the state of psychological emotions which lead to severe pressure that may cost him his carrier.

4.3 The concept of self esteem

The self-esteem is "*a concept and an orientation that expresses the individual's perception of himself and his ability to do all his actions and actions. This perception is embodied in the needs of childhood, especially the need for independence, freedom, acceptance and success*". (Mustafa Fahmi, 1987, p. 245)

4.4 Psychological pressures on referees

It is when the referee feels his inability to face the events or the requirements of his profession and which poses a threat to him. It causes a high rate of negative emotions, accompanied by physiological and behavioral changes in response to the warning of those pressures

4.5 Football referees

The referee is the person who meets special conditions and includes passing the physical and technical tests, and in light of these results, this person gets adopted by the competent federation and then classified into a class or referees' category in accordance with special instructions. (Jassem Abbas, 2002, p.24)

The referees can be defined as a group of sports persons who have been given the executive authority of the law of football during, before and after the football game when assigned to manage it. They are of two types:

Central referee who performs inside the playground, two assistant referees who stand on the side lines, and a fourth assistant referee who stay completely outside the playground. Referees are categorized into internationals by the FIFA. They lead an international indoor and outdoor match and the referees of the first, second and third grades are accredited by the national federation and lead only an internal match. (Samir Muhanna, 2000, p. 6)

In football, there are three referees on the playground, one as central referee and two assistant referees who watch the sidelines among other duties, and there is a fourth

referee who is often in charge of external duties or replaces if necessary the assistant referees when they cannot finish the match.

5. Methodology of study

In this study, the descriptive approach has been adopted for being relevant to the subject of the research as the methodology in scientific research is a set of rules and foundations that are developed in order to reach the truth.

The research methodology differs depending on the subject topics dealt with; this is why there several types of scientific methods. In line with the nature of the current study, we have relied on the descriptive approach in the method of associative surveys, where it aims to try to determine the relationship between two measurable variables.

The descriptive approach is based on a survey that focuses on a phenomenon as it exists in the present, and this is what the current study is trying to prove, through revealing the relationship between the level of psychological stress and the level of self-esteem, using a combination of tools.

5.1 Community and sample of the study

"The community of research is a group of elements having a characteristic or several characteristics that distinguish them from other elements being scrutinized or investigated" (Maurice Angers, 2006, p. 298). The community of this study represents the referees who actively perform in the super league for the season 2017/2018, registered in the Algerian National Football Federation with a total of 170 referees. The sample of the research was deliberately chosen with 80 referees from the total society.

5.2 Fields of study

A. Time frame: The theoretical study began in March 2017 after which applied study began in April 2017, which lasted about three months up to June. This period was applied in the field and analysis of the results obtained, using statistical methods.

B. Space frame: The study was conducted on the professional football association that supervises the referees through the training sessions established and precisely during the physical tests and sessions, which allowed us to communicate with the referees and distribute the scales at the same time.

C. Human field: It is basically restricted to the elite referees active in the first professional football association.

5.3 Description of study tools

A. Resources and references: In this study, we have relied on a set of references that are relevant to the subject, ranging from books, magazines, articles and memoirs to the subject of psychological stress and self-esteem.

B. The two scales: We have reviewed many studies and research, especially in social psychology, which dealt with the subject of psychological stress and self-esteem. In this research we used the self-assessment scale prepared by Hussein Abdel-Aziz El-Derini and Mohamed Ahmed Osama, Abdel Wahab Mohamed Kamel, which was applied and adapted by Prof. Bachir Maamria on the Algerian environment. The scale consists of 30 items that measure self-esteem (Bechir Maamria, the rationing lists of self-esteem on the Algerian environment, the Department of Social Sciences, University of Haj Lakhdar Batna). And the scale of sources of psychological pressure and degree of intensity on the rulers of football from their point of view in Algeria, and included the following axes:

Table 1: The axes and their expressions

Axis	Title of the proposed axis	Number of axis expression	Expression numbers
The first axis	Fear of physical abuse	08	1-11-16-22-29-32-39-43
The second axis	Disagreement with colleagues	07	42-02-08-13-18-25-35-41
The third axis	Rewards and incentives	08	4-20-28-37-51-53-55
The fourth axis	Conflict of social dimension	07	3-6-10-15-19-24-34
The fifth axis	The media	09	5-9-17-23-30-44-47-49-56
The sixth axis	Physical condition and time	08	12-26-33-46-52-57-60-62
The seventh axis	fear of failure	11	7-14-21-31-38-40-45-48-59-61-63
The eighth axis	Personal conflict	05	27-36-50-54-58

It is answered by a five rating scale that is classified according to the following classification:

Degree of applicability of the expression				
Applies perfectly	Applies significantly	Medium	Few	Never

5.4 Statistical analysis and processing method

After the implementation phase, the data were uploaded in the computer for analysis and processing through the statistical program SPSS, in order to discuss hypotheses in the light of the research objectives. We used the following statistical methods:

- Calculation of the Pearson correlation coefficient, to study the correlations between the dimensions of the scale expressions and hence the reliability of the instrument, and the correlation between the two measurements.
- Calculation of Alpha Cronbach equation, correlation coefficients in standardization and determination, stability of the search tool.
- Simple Moving Average and Standard deviation.

6. View and analysis of the results

6.1 Personal and organizational characteristics of study sample members

Table 2: Distribution of sample members according to individual characteristics

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage %
Scientific level	Non-university scientific level	29	37.2
	University-scientific level	49	62.5
Marital status	Married	24	30.8
	Single	54	69.2
Level of arbitration	Main referee	28	35.9
	Assistant of arbitration	50	64.1
Statutes of me government	National rule	68	87.2
	International druse	10	12.8
Referees profession	Employee	54	69.2
	Free works	24	30.8
The age	Less than 25	17	21.49
	25-34	42	53.84
	35 and above	19	24.35
Experience	Less than 4 years	20	25.64
	From 5 to years	35	44.87
	More than 10 years	23	29.48

Table 2 shows that 30.8% of the sample are married, compared with 69.2% of the singles. This divergence in the results of the study sample is normal and the majority of the sample is young and still at the beginning of their lives. In recent years, the age of marriage has been delayed in our country, whether male or female.

In terms of the level of study, we also obtained (37.2%) for the referees who are less than the university level, compared to 62.8% of those who reached university level.

As for the arbitral roles, we obtained 35.9% of the main referees, 64.1%. It is normal for the number of assistant referees to be doubled to the referees. Each referee has two assistant referees. The referees' profession is limited to two options: The results

showed that 69.2% of the referees were employees and 30.8% were freelancers. This may be due to the fact that most of the studied sample holds the university level, which enables them to obtain the job with some kind of ease.

As for the status of the government as a national rule or beyond it to an international rule, the results were (12.8%) international rule and (87.2%) national rule and this is due to the fact that all Algerian international rulers 12 rule and the difficulty of upgrading to the rank of international rule.

The percentage of referees with less than 50 years' professional experience was 25.64%. The percentage of referees who ranged from 5-9 years was 44.87% (10.4 years and above) with a ratio of 29.48%. These percentages reflect the intention of the arbitrators to rely more on the experienced persons due to the difficulty of the task in the professional league matches, which is the highest national level.

As for the age of rulers, it was divided into three categories, the first category was less than 25 years, 21.49%, the second group (25-34 years), 53.84%, and the last group, 35 years, were 24.35% Figures indicate that the largest proportion is between the ages of 25 and 35 years and this indicates the efforts of the Supervisory Authority to arbitrate this sector without neglecting the experience factor to invest the government for a long time and give opportunities to obtain the largest international rulers.

6.2 Levels of self-esteem for football referees

Table 3: The levels of self-esteem for football referees

The Total Sample N = 75				Level of Self-Esteem
Percentage	Repetitions	Standard Deviation	Arithmetic Average	Above Average
72%	54	0.452	4,720	Average
28%	21			

From the above chart, we notice that the level of self-esteem for football referees is between average and above average. The first with repetition 54 and a percentage of 72%, whereas the average, repetition 21 and a percentage of 28%.

6.3 Levels of psychological pressure for football referees

Table 4: Levels of exposure to different sources of psychological pressure

Statistical Significance	K 2	Level of pressure		The themes	
		High	Low		
0.024	5.12	49	29	Repetition	Fear from physical harm
		62.82	37.17	Percentage	
0.001	11.53	24	54	Repetition	Conflicts with colleagues
		30.8	69.2	Percentage	
0.00	18.51	58	20	Repetition	Rewards & incentives
		74.6	25.6	Percentage	
0.00	14.82	56	22	Repetition	Conflicts of social dimension
		71.8	28.2	Percentage	
0.001	49.28	70	8	Repetition	The media
		89.7	10.3	Percentage	
0.174	1.84	33	45	Repetition	Physical condition & time
		42.3	57.7	Percentage	
0.003	8.66	52	26	Repetition	Fear from failure
		66.66	33.33	Percentage	
0.07	3.28	47	31	Repetition	Personal conflicts
		60.25	39.74	Percentage	
0.003	8.66	53	26	Repetition	Total degree of sources of psychological stress
		66.7	33.3	Percentage	

It appears from the Table 4 that referees are subject to a high level of pressure 66.7%.

The results are

- The theme of media, its percentage 89.7%.
- The theme of rewards & incentives, its percentage 74.6%.
- The theme of Social dimensions, its percentage 71.8%.
- The theme of fear from failure, its percentage 66.66%.
- The theme of fear from physical harm, its percentage 62.82%.
- The theme of personal conflicts, its percentage 60.25%

While pressure was low on the theme:

- The theme of the physical status & time 57.7%.
- The theme of conflicts with colleagues 69.2%.
- The actual study has revealed a high degree of suffering of the football referees; the levels of pressure reached 67.7%. These results are relatively consistent with previous studies achieved in different Arab & Western societies.
- The study done by Ibrahim (2000) classified referees into classes (first, second and third) and how they are subjects to a lot of psychological pressure while they manage the match.

- The study of Wolfsan & Neave (2000) confirmed that 71% of them feel physical exhaustion after the end of the competition.
- Winbridge & Richardson (1990) supported these results. 45% of basketball referees confirmed that the job of a referee is a challenge itself and they are subjects to a lot of psychological pressure, muscle tension and high blood pressure.
- Although the degree of psychological pressure is different depending on the game itself and the culture, certain studies confirm that the performance of the referee depends on many psychological factors which will lead to physical & mental exhaustion, this will eventually affect his performance and his ability of controlling his judgments (Haroon 1997 & Mustapha 2001 and Constbal, 1996).
- All these results indicate the existence of a high pressure with referees and this is considered something logical due to the nature of the job and to the criticism from the media. Referees are always blamed and accused from the trainers and the audience for the defeats, in addition to many verbal & physical attacks every week.
- Finally, referees are permanently exposed to a lot of psychological pressure according to most of the studies.

Table 5: The relationship between level of self-esteem and level of psychological stress

Level of self-esteem					Dimensions of psychological stress sources
Statistical Significance	Degree of freedom	Moral potential	Level of significance	The calculated value R	
Significant	72	0.03	0.05	0.24	Fear of physical abuse
Significant	72	0.02	0.05	0.17	Conflicts with colleagues
Significant	72	0.001	0.05	0.37	Rewards and incentives
Significant	72	0.01	0.05	0.29	Opposition with the social dimension
Significant	72	0.004	0.05	0.32	The media
Significant	72	0.003	0.05	0.38	Physical status and time
Significant	72	0.02	0.05	0.25	Fear of failure
Significant	72	0.001	0.05	0.19	Personal conflict

7. General Summary

In this study, we tried to show the relationship of sources of psychological stress at the level of self-estimation of the referee for the first national division. The main and important idea that we derived from this research and based on our applied study, using our research tools and after analyzing and extracting the results, we found that the football referee has an average and above average estimation and this is the result of the psychological stress before, during, and after the administration of the games.

The Media are at the forefront of the most important source of psychological pressure, which is reflected on the personality of the referee in general and on the level of self-estimation in particular and all the comments and writings of the sports press are reflected on the quality of the relationship between the referees on the one hand, coaches, players, managers and the public on the other. These results are corresponded to Nilson & Naf study (2007), where the results indicate through the permanent blame on the referees that although the referees admit to making some mistakes, they point out that these errors are an opportunity to develop. Also, the results corresponded to what Nabil Nada indicated (2009) where he considered media as an effective source of pressure especially the written words on the day of game or the day after as well as Radio and Television.

The source of fear of failure comes second in terms of the impact on the level of self-estimation, and this indicates the keenness of the referees, their determination to succeed and the fear of making mistakes, all this increases their pressure and affects their concentration and psychological consensus. The referees considered that the Algerian Spectators do not forgive mistakes and have a pre-judgment about the unfairness of the referees and always object to the decisions as the players often contribute in fueling the situation; The result is consistent with the study of Ziad Tahayneh (2006), which dealt with the relationship between psychological pressure and intentions of the referees to retire, where he pointed out that among the main factors there is the fear of performance. Mohammed Hassan Allawi (1998) emphasizes that the sensibility and fear of failure is the ability to have fun in sports performance without being very depressed when the referee makes mistakes or even when he makes a series of mistakes. As Nabil Ahmed (2009) points out that the causes of psychological pressure is the preoccupation of the referee by comparing his level with his outstanding colleagues, and due to his preoccupation with it very much without looking for methods to upgrade his level, and also due to his attribution of the decline of the level to external factors and external control, which indicates the difficulty of correcting his

mistakes and accepting tips and draining time in the quarrels which exhausts him to the degree of combustion .

The incentive and rewards factor increases human motivation for work, creativity and challenge, but the lack of incentives or lack of suitability to the effort inevitably influences performance and increases the stress associated with the work. Herzberg considered the person to be motivated by his surroundings and focused on the variables in the environment: Policies of the Organization, methods of management, working conditions, etc.

There are many theories that dealt with motivation and its impact on the productivity of the individual. The referees consider that their income is weaker compared to many countries of the world as there is a lack of conviction in the manner and the means of evaluation. The referee does not only insist on the material aspect, but wants to feel that he is doing a valuable work ,he is facing lot of work challenges to overcome and wants also to be appreciated. Money is not the supernatural catalyst, otherwise why does a wealthy person want to continue working? Man seeks to be treated as a human being, he wants to stay and live as a respected human being who has his thoughts, personality, friends, and successes and has an influence in his field of work.

The physical condition plays a significant role in all players' performance. The referees are no different from the rest of the players where they need a daily physical preparation that enables them to keep up with the different stages of the game and any disorder in the physical preparation will be disastrous. Amer al-Khikani study (2005), which dealt with physical fitness and some psychological variables of the referee of the first degree in football and their relationship to the level of the performance, concluded that there is a real positive relationship between the physical fitness of the referees and their level of performance. Abdul Rahman Al-Zahrani study (2002) dealt with the effect of anxiety and confidence on concentration of attention and response speed. The researcher recommended that the referees should pay attention to the applied exercises that increase the concentration of attention and the speed of reaction.

The practice of sports of all kinds contributes to the social interaction between individuals, and referees interact with other members of the sports community, but in many cases, this interaction results in psychological stress that affects the self-estimation of the referee during or after the game or even before. Susan Kanani study (1994), an analytical study of the Personalities of the referees of the Olympic Games in Jordan, showed that there were statistically significant differences in the characteristics of the social dimension, the psychological situation and the consult for the international

referees, and that the best characteristics of the three dimensions of the personality in the sample of the research were in moral values, social status and courage.

Referees consider that the large number of transportations, daily trainings and the conditions of their occupations deprive them of doing their familial or social duties and it is difficult for the referees to spend long time with them, as they consider that the profession of arbitration affects their personality in front of others, therefore they are touched of the verbal abuse and harassments which occur every week.

8. Suggestions

- Knowing the most important psychological pressures that affect the level of self-estimation and can only come through the use of academic experts with scientific knowledge of how to detect the psychological pressure of the referees and know the appropriate strategy to treat it well. This strategy means helping the referees to overcome the pressures of work by providing medical and treatment services and providing them with counseling services and appropriate preventive measures through an integrated team of doctors and psychologists.
- Alert the referees to the need to know the impact of excessive pressure on their personality and the need to recognize the causes in order to reduce them.
- Periodic meetings between referees and journalists to explain the laws of the game and the difficulties which affect the performance of the referees, including in particular the impact of the press's criticism of the referees and the impact on the actions of players and supporters towards the referees.
- Making lot of short traineeships that allow the referees to exchange views and analysis of some games to take advantage of the mistakes made by others.
- the officials of the arbitral tribunal need to move away from authoritarian methods in dealing with the referees and give them the rights of dialogues and express opinions without fear of sanctions.
- Conduct periodic sessions with trainers and representatives of the players and even representatives of the Committee of the supporters to explain the laws and difficulties in the task of arbitration, and the effects of harassments and provocative words and their reflection on his personal life and his family's life
- Calling for the transparency of the weekly evaluation and to informing the referees of their points and reasons for their failure and urge them to make efforts. This evaluation is translated in the form of appropriate systems of reward and punishment, because they are a significant part of the sources that cause the pressures of work in many cases. Moreover, it is need a Re-examining of

incentive systems and evaluating performance at appropriate periodic intervals to ensure that these systems are achieved which represents an appropriate strategy provided with rewarding the best referee every week or at least per month.

- Organizing a clear and transparent assessment ladder to be discussed with the referees to give their appropriate suggestions.

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